

SOCIAL POLICY OF UZBEKISTAN ON PROTECTING THE HEALTH OF THE POPULATION IN EMERGENCY SITUATIONS

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Abstract. *The article discusses the implementation of the social policy of Uzbekistan on protecting the health of the population in an emergency situation.*

Key words: *Social policy, population, health care, emergency situation.*

As is known, an emergency situation (ES) is a situation in a certain territory that has arisen as a result of an accident, a dangerous natural phenomenon, a disaster, the spread of a disease that poses a danger to others, a natural or other disaster that may result or has resulted in human casualties, damage human health or the environment, significant material losses and disruption of human living conditions (1).

It should be noted that in emergency situations, a significant part of the population often finds itself without shelter, food, water, medical care, and basic necessities. In this regard, the task of preserving the health of victims or people caught in the affected area is acute.

A prompt solution to the problem of protecting the health of the population, especially during the initial period of emergency response, is one of the primary tasks of government authorities. It has been established that over the years of independence, the republic has created an integral state system for protecting the population and territories from natural disasters, man-made accidents and catastrophes, the necessary regulatory framework has been formed, and significant work has been done in terms of scale and content to prevent and eliminate emergency situations, as well as to prepare the population. to actions in case of disasters. However, the analysis of the current emergency prevention and response system revealed a number of problematic issues that negatively affect the protection of the population and territory of the republic from the threats of natural disasters, catastrophes and man-made accidents. To implement state policy in the field of ensuring the vital interests of the individual, society and the state, there is a legislative framework regulating the activities of state authorities, enterprises and organizations, as well as self-government bodies of citizens in the field of civil protection. The laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the protection of the population and territories from emergencies of a natural and man-made nature” and “On civil protection” have been adopted, as well as a number of resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan (2.3) Effective measures to strengthen the forces and means of civil protection units, training of management bodies and training the population to provide first aid have made it possible in recent years to reduce the number of victims in emergency situations. However, despite the significant efforts and financial costs directed by khokimiyats, ministries and departments to combat accidents, catastrophes and natural disasters, material losses from their impact are not reduced. This is largely due to the fact that, as a rule, work was carried out to eliminate emergency situations that had already manifested themselves, and to a lesser extent this concerned the issues of preserving the health of the victims.

In order to implement these tasks, the Ministry of Emergency Situations, together with interested ministries and departments of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regional khokimiyats and the city of Tashkent, has developed a State program for forecasting and preventing emergency situations.

The basis of the State Program included materials from targeted programs developed by specialists from a number of ministries, departments and organizations in accordance with the Work Plan of the expert group for the development of the Concept and the State Program. To this day, the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan maintains a high level of threat from emergencies of a natural and man-made nature, a tendency to increase their number and scale of consequences, which forces us to look for new solutions to the problem of preserving the health of the population and protecting territories from emergency situations, to anticipate future threats, risks and hazards, to develop methods of their forecast and prevention. In this regard, recently serious attention has been paid to the issues of protecting the population and territories from emergency situations. The initial stage of creating the State System of Prevention and Action in Emergency Situations has been completed, during which the tasks of rescuing the population affected by accidents, catastrophes and natural disasters were mainly solved. However, the current state of the State System of Emergency Situations (SSES) and the level of development of its subsystems are such that they do not yet fully provide a comprehensive solution to the problem of preserving public health and protecting territories from emergency situations. The main task of the next stage of development of the State system of prevention and action in emergency situations is the early implementation of a set of measures aimed at preventing and maximally reducing the risks of emergencies situations, as well as to preserve human health, reduce material losses and damage to the environment. The goal of state policy at this stage in accordance with this State Program is to ensure a guaranteed level of protection of the population and territories from emergency situations, reducing risks and mitigating the consequences of accidents, catastrophes and natural disasters in the republic, taking into account the achievements of domestic science and technology, as well as world experience in this field. The most optimal mechanism for the practical implementation of the main provisions of state policy in the field of preventing emergency situations and reducing their consequences is the implementation of measures under a number of targeted programs. In order to ensure the effective implementation of state policy in the field of protecting the population and territories from emergency situations, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to radically improve the efficiency of the system for preventing and eliminating emergency situations” was adopted, which identifies the most important areas for improving the activities of the system for preventing and eliminating emergency situations and tasks of the Ministry of Emergency Situations of the Republic of Uzbekistan (4).

In accordance with the decree, the Center for Hydrometeorological Service, the State Inspectorate for Control and Supervision of the Technical Condition and Safety of Operation of Large and Particularly Important Water Facilities under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the State Inspectorate for Small Vessels, as well as the Service were transferred to the system of the Ministry of Emergency Situations of the Republic of Uzbekistan urgent reports from the Institute of Seismology of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In connection with the transfer of the above organizations, new main tasks of the Ministry of Emergency Situations of the Republic of Uzbekistan have been defined, in particular:

-development and ensuring the implementation of a unified state policy in the field of prevention and response to natural and man-made emergencies in peacetime and war, hydrometeorology, sustainable operation of hydraulic structures, seismic observations, safe operation of small vessels, protection of the life and health of citizens on water bodies;

- early identification of risk factors and threats of emergency situations, ensuring early prevention and prevention of their occurrence and other tasks. Thus, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan is aimed at strengthening the capacity and expanding the lower level of the system of the Ministry of Emergency Situations by creating additional departments for emergency situations and rescue teams in areas (cities) characterized by a high risk of emergency situations leading to a negative impact on the physical, mental and spiritual health of the population.

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